

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF INTERNATIONAL CURRENCY FINANCIAL CREDIT RELATIONS

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Abstract: *This article discusses the theoretical foundations of international currency and credit relations.*

Key words: *national currency, economic stability, export, import, monetary policy.*

Money plays an important role in the economy of any country. Money relations of society such as production, distribution, circulation and consumption covers processes, conditions for extended reproduction creates. Money and economy are interrelated elements. If there are problems in the society's economy, then of course such problems has a negative impact on the money circulation of the society. In economic theory, real money exists as a commodity equivalent, satisfies the transactional needs of consumers. Paper money is a representative of the value of real money in circulation.

Any independent country has its own money, and such money is for this country is the national currency. The national currency has its own name and a certain circulation history. Economic security has its objects and subjects, and its object is the country's economic system and its constituent elements.

The national money of a certain country is its national currency. For this country, the national currency units of other countries are foreign currencies. For example, the US dollar, British pound sterling, Canadian dollar, French franc, Japanese yen, Turkish lira and similar freely circulating currencies are foreign currencies in the Republic of Uzbekistan. , in turn, Uzbek "soum" is considered a foreign currency for these countries.

According to the characteristics of their circulation in the world market, currencies are divided into freely circulating, partially or completely restricted, closed or exotic currencies. National currency units of some countries are limited to go abroad and circulate there based on existing and active laws regarding currency relations in these countries.

International currency relations developed in the context of the emergence of the world market, the deepening of the international division of labor, the growth of production forces, the formation of the world economic system, the internationalization and globalization of economic relations. International currency relations is a set of social relations formed in connection with the use of currency in the world economy and serving the mutual exchange of the results of activities of national economies. [1]

Some elements of currency relations appeared in the ancient world, in ancient Greece and Rome, in the form of promissory notes and currency exchange. These relations were realized with bills of exchange (drafts).

It developed in the medieval "bill fairs" of Lyon, Antwerp, and other trading centers of Western Europe. During the period of formation of feudalism and capitalist mode of production, the system of international settlements implemented through banks began to form. International currency relations include international economic relations related to the process of material production, i.e. primary production relations and distribution, exchange and consumption processes. There is a direct (to there are direct) and consequential (reverse) relationships. Their objective basis is the process of social production that creates international exchange of goods, capital, and services. Xalqaro amaliyotda valyutalaming quyidagi turlari mavjud:

- Freely usable currency (freely usable currency) - payment currency restrictions in the current operations section of the balance sheet national currencies of countries without.

- Hard currency - economically and politically.

currencies of countries considered stable with a stable exchange rate.

- Soft currency - international payment.

which cannot perform the function of a tool, i.e. has external convertibility foreign currencies.

- International reserve currencies (reserve currency) - of the world

leading currencies that are accepted as means of international payment in all countries.

The reason for the fluctuation of the nominal exchange rate of the US dollar one of the main factors is the large deficit of the country's trade balance. As of January 1, 2020, the deficit of the US trade balance is 466.3 billion. reached the dollar. This is a huge deficit.

The instability of international reserve currency rates has a negative impact on the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The reason for this is that the nominal exchange rate of our national currency, the soum, is determined against the US dollar, which is the main reserve currency. Therefore, the instability of the US dollar exchange rate directly affects the stability of the nominal exchange rate of the soum.

Therefore, international reserve currency exchange rates taking into account its instability, in order to ensure the stability of the nominal exchange rate of the soum, the national currency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the proposal to introduce the determination of its exchange rate in relation to the "currency basket" consisting of the US dollar, euro and Japanese yen is of great importance . As a result, the fluctuation range of the nominal exchange rate of the soum is significantly reduced.

One of the first theories about the exchange rate is the purchasing power theory of currencies, and this theory is based on the theoretical views of English economists D. Hume and D. Ricardo. According to D. Ricardo, the deficit of the

trade balance led to a decrease in the value of sterling, the purchasing power of currencies is determined by the ratio of their amount in circulation. The main rule of the theory of purchasing power of currencies is that the exchange rate is determined by the relative value of the currencies of two countries, and in turn, the relative value of currencies depends on the level of prices. It is characteristic that, according to this theory, the price of goods and services is determined by the amount of money in circulation. The founders of the theory of purchasing power of currencies put forward the idea of determining a moderate exchange rate that allows to ensure a balanced state of the balance of payments.

The purchasing power theory of currencies is the first scientifically was founded in 1918 by the Swedish economist G. Kassel. According to him, under moderate trade conditions, such an exchange rate is formed that reflects the purchasing power of the relevant currency. [2]

It is clear from the opinion of G. Kassel that the exchange rate formation is directly related to the purchasing power of the currency, and the main attention is paid to the quantity. In the theory of the purchasing power of the currency, the objective factors affecting the formation of the exchange rate and the cases of influence on them by the Central Bank are not taken into account. However, among the factors affecting the formation of the exchange rate at the present time, there are objective factors such as political factors, speculative capitalization factors play an important role.

The founder of the theory of regulated currencies J.M. Keynes is. The reason for the emergence of this theory is the world economic crisis that occurred in 1929-1933.

The theory of floating exchange rates is a unique theory among exchange rate theories. The founders of this theory are economists belonging to the neoclassical trend. They include M. Friedman, F. Mahlup, A. Lindbeck, Johnson, L. Erhard, G. Girsch, E. Durrllam can be included. [3]

Another theory about the exchange rate is defined is the theory of parities and exchange rates. According to this theory, exchange rate fluctuations are an ineffective way of regulating the balance of payments. Because foreign trade does not sufficiently react to the fluctuations of the price in international markets due to changes in exchange rates. An increase in the demand for imports leads to an increase in the demand for foreign currencies.

In this case, the exchange rate in conditions of balanced export and import corresponds to a short-term periodic interval. During this period, foreign currency in the amount of excess demand will not be available in the market. Therefore, the value of the currency increases, and the temporary periodic gap does not arise in the process of interaction between the supply of foreign currencies and the exchange rate of the national currency.

Assessing the practical value of exchange rate theories is important from the point of view of their viability. Therefore, in order to assess the practical importance of this theoretical view of F. Makhlop, on the example of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the conditions of balance between export and import, we will consider the effect of the supply of currencies on the national exchange rate.

The general conclusion is that the change of the real exchange rate depends on the rate of change of the national price, that is, nominal devaluation does not always lead to real devaluation. For example, if the growth rate of the national currency rate is higher than the growth rate of domestic prices, then the real exchange rate will decrease, that is, the price of imported goods expressed in the national currency will increase compared to the prices of national goods. Internal price equalization in the future (the level of consumption and indexation is equal to 1) occurs during the period of changes between the prices of imported and national goods depending on the contribution of imported goods to the volume of gross consumer products. If the growth rate of the exchange rate is lower than the growth

rate of domestic prices, then the import goods prices decrease compared to the prices of national goods, accordingly, despite the nominal devaluation, real devaluation occurs. And finally, if the growth rate of the nominal exchange rate is equal to the growth rate of domestic prices, then the real exchange rate will not change.

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